

A Critical Review on the Need for an Effective National Policy on the Social Sciences for India*

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Abstract

In this paper, the author dwells on the need for a national policy on the social sciences.

Key Words: policy, social sciences, bilingualism, secularism, documentary films,

Introduction

I am very happy to be with you on this auspicious occasion of the celebration of the one hundredth birth anniversary of noted sociologist, Prof. A.R.Desai. Prof. Desai is a pioneer of the Marxian approach to study Indian society (Desai, 1986).

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I think Desai's essay "Relevance of the Marxist Approach to the Study of Indian Society" (Desai, 1986) should be made compulsory reading for every student of Indian Sociology, because it not only highlights the problems facing Indian Sociology but brings with it a fresh approach to the study of Indian reality which is radically different from all previous approaches.

That apart, Desai pioneered the study of Indian nationalism from a Marxist angle (Desai, 1984), contributed to the study of rural sociology, urban sociology and social movements. Desai has now been recognized as a key sociological thinker and he has become part and parcel of textbooks on Indian sociological thought, like Nagla's Indian Sociological Thought. (Nagla, 2008). Bengali textbooks have also incorporated chapters on Desai (Mukhopadhyay, 2012). This seminar is a fitting tribute to Desai's contributions.

Why do we need A National Policy on Social Sciences?

In this session, we will be dealing with the state of social sciences in India. Let us first clarify what we mean by the term "social sciences". The Concise Oxford Dictionary(Ninth Edition, 1995) defined social sciences as 1.the scientific study of human society and social relations, and 2.a branch of this (politics or economics)The Oxford Dictionary of Sociology(2007) defined social sciences as a general label applied to the study of human and social relationships. I have operationally defined "social sciences" as those disciplines dealing with the evolution, structure and functioning of human societies, the impact of environment and symbolic communications, etc.(Banerjee, 2003, p. 86).The report of Gulbenkian

Commission entitled "Open the Social Sciences" identified five disciplines -History, Economics, Political Science, Sociology, and Anthropology. (Banerjee A. , 2013, p. 3) To this list we may add the discipline of Social Psychology .

Social sciences in India are badly and sadly neglected .For their proper development, we need a National Policy on the Social Sciences. The dictionary definition of 'policy' means "a course or principle of action adopted or proposed by a government , party, business or individual"(The Concise Oxford Dictionary of Current English, Ninth Edition, 1995).The European Union is today adopting policies for improving the state of their societies, based on recommendations of their Joint Research Committee.

In her 'Foreword' to the book *From Input to Impact* , Máire Georghegan Quinn, European Commissioner for Research, wrote:

"Policy makers need to be presented with options based upon the best scientific evidence that is integrated across all relevant disciplines , from natural science and engineering to socio-economic" 1.

India has already a National Policy on Science & Technology .Thanks to such a policy, India has advanced a lot in the scientific field. The latest such achievement is India's Mars Orbiter Mission, the Mangalyan.Unfortunately , despite such advances in science and technology , Indian society is still in a state of backwardness. According to the Human Development Index introduced by United Nations Development Programme in 1990, India

¹ Máire Georghegan Quinn:'Foreword' to *From Input to Impact: A Selection of Highlights of JRC Activities* , JRC European Commission , Luxembourg, 2011,p.5.

's ranks 126 out of 177 countries.² Our development policies need to be based on the best scientific research available. As Yogendra Singh rightly pointed out,

The most widely acknowledged level of social science relevance relates to the contributions researchers make in the formulation and implementation of policies of social welfare and development . (Singh, 2005, p. 196)

But unless and until we are able to attract the best talent available to the social sciences, we will never be able to improve the quality of human life in India. For this we need a policy for development of the social sciences.

Historical Background

Social sciences in India developed under the colonial regime. As Yogendra Singh (Singh, 2005, p. 197) rightly observed:"The British rule contributed in an unprecedented measure to the institutional, organizational and administrative innovations , establishing the legitimacy of policy oriented research ." So , it will be worthwhile to briefly examine the role of the British in carrying out policies for development of the social sciences in India.

We should be aware that the British did not engage in the development of the social sciences out of any altruism. Near the end of his famous essay "The British rule in India", Karl Marx rightly pointed out :

England, it is true is causing a social revolution in Hindustan, was actuated only by the vilest interests and was stupid in the manner of enforcing them. But that is not

² Cited in Sheobahal Singh :*Sociology of Development* , Rawat Publications, 2010,p.18.

the question. The question is, can mankind fulfill its destiny without a fundamental revolution in the social state of Asia? If not, whatever may have been the crimes of England, she was the unconscious tool of history in bringing about the revolution³.

Indeed, national interest was the sole motivating force behind the decision of the British to patronize the social sciences. And, as Marx correctly pointed out, they brought about a social revolution. The British were completely an alien race. In order to secure their rule in India they had to know the customs, traditions, folkways and mores of the various communities of India, the traditional laws which govern them, their currency systems of Indians and so on.

Srinivas and Panini (Srinivas, 1986, pp. 18-19) delineated three phases in the development of the social sciences in India .

1773-1900.The Foundations are laid

1901-1950.Era of Professionalization

Post -Independence years-Heightened research activity

The Foundations (1773-1900)

The earliest attempt by the British to sponsor social research were spontaneous . In 1757, the British won control of Bengal subah by defeating Nawab Siraj-ud Dowlah in the Battle of Plassey. After assuming the administration of Bengal, the British felt the need to collect data on the natives of Bengal.

³ Karl Marx:"The British Rule in India" in K.Marx and F.Engels :The First Indian War of Independence , foreign Languages Publishing House, Moscow,(N.D.)p.20

This need was evident in a statement by Henry Verelst , then Governor of Bengal (1769) on the necessity to collect data about the leading families of Bengal and an inquiry into the customs of the natives. This statement may be regarded as the beginning of the colonial policy on the social sciences. (Banerjee, 2007, p. 126).Since the late 18th century, we find a number of attempts to found scholarly societies ,and do social surveys , many of which won the support of the colonial administration. Among them was the foundation of the Asiatic Society by William Jones in 1787.Indology was founded. In 1807, Francis Buchanan undertook the first government sponsored ethnographic survey of Bengal. In 1822,Thomas Munro ordered an enquiry into the state of indigenous education. In 1823,Monstuart Elphinstone collected data on education in Bombay. This survey was followed by an enquiry into the state of education by the judicial department in 1829 and another survey in 1835-38 by Adams in Bengal. All these enquiries collected a wealth of data on the state of education .In the process, they also collected sociological data. In 1871, the first Census was undertaken.

The 19th century also witnessed the growth of scholarly associations. The Bethune Society and the Bengal Social Science Association grew up to promote social science research were patronized by the British . (Dutt Gupta, 1972) Comte's sociology made a great impact on the leading Bengali intellectuals of the nineteenth century. This resulted in the foundation of the Indian Positivist Society (Forbes, 1975)

1901-1950.Era of Professionalization

At the turn of the 20th century, the Indian National Movement was gaining in strength. The decision of Lord Curzon to partition Bengal led to the Swadeshi Movement in Bengal(1905-1911)⁴. An offshoot of the Swadeshi Movement was the establishment of National Council of Education (1906). From this period we find indigenous experiments in education. The first Sociology Department in India was established in Mysore University in the native state of Mysore in 1917. In 1921, the first undergraduate course in Sociology was also introduced in Mysore University. This marks the beginning of an indigenous policy on the social sciences in India. The first Sociology Department in British India was established in Bombay University 1919 under the stewardship of Prof. Patrick Geddes. In 1921, a combined Department of Sociology and Social Anthropology was established in Lucknow University. In 1945, the Anthropological Survey of India was established. B.S. Guha was its first Director. This indicates that the Government of India realized the need of anthropological research.

1951-present: Planning and the Social Sciences

India won Independence on 15th August, 1947. In that same year (1947-48) the first Education Commission of independent India was set up under the Chairmanship of Dr. Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan. The commission recommended the establishment of new fields of post-graduate teaching and research which included the social sciences. In 1951, the Indian Sociological Society was established and Indian

Sociology was institutionalised. In 1958, the Government of India adopted a Scientific Policy Resolution. By virtue of this resolution, the government set up many research organizations. The Planning Commission created a Research Committee for financing social science research but the bulk of the funding went to Economics.

In 1966, the Planning Commission recommended setting up the Indian Council of Social Science Research (ICSSR). Three years later, the ICSSR was set up in 1969. Since then the ICSSR has played a major role in promoting social science research. According to a recent brochure distributed by the ICSSR Eastern Regional Centre, the following are its major activities:

- 1) To maintain a collection of books and periodicals in the social sciences.
- 2) To undertake publications and assist in publication of journals and books in the social sciences.
- 3) To support bibliographical work, especially in regional languages.
- 4) To organize and support conference, seminars and workshops in the region.
- 5) To grant partial support for research projects conducted in the region.
- 6) To assist visiting scholars, invited by ICSSR under Cultural Exchange Programme.
- 7) To maintain a Guest House for visiting scholars.

Among the disciplines recognized by the ICSSR as social sciences are Economics, Commerce, Management, Business

⁴ See Sumit Sarkar: The Swadeshi Movement in Bengal, Permanent Black, 2011.

Administration, Sociology and Social Anthropology, Social work, Demography, Gender studies, Political Science, International Relations, Geography, Legal Studies, Public Administration, Psychology, Education, Criminology, Other -Linguistics, National Security studies, etc. The ICSSR also lays stress on interdisciplinary research.⁵ The number of disciplines covered by the ICSSR far exceeds the categories identified by the Gulbenkian Commission.

In 1966, the Kothari Commission on Education recommended Socially Useful & Productive Work in school. But no policy statement was made with respect to teaching or research in social sciences. In 1986, the National Policy on Education proposed to give adequate support to teaching and research in the social sciences. The University Grants Commission prepared a Model Syllabus which included the social sciences. In 2004, Indian sociologists debated on the need for a National Policy on the Social Sciences at the XXX All India Sociological Conference at Gorakhpur, where social scientists have presented papers on the relevance of a national policy on the social sciences. Two symposia were devoted to the analysis of the need for a national policy on the social sciences⁶. That apart, papers were also presented in the Research Committees⁷. But,

⁵ Vide ICSSR-ERC-Indian Council of Social Science Research, Ministry of Human Resource Development, Eastern Regional Centre.

⁶ See Manvendra Pratap Singh ed. 30 All India Sociological Conference, Gorakhpur, December 27-29, 2004, National Policy on Social Sciences, Souvenir & Abstracts, Organized by Department of sociology, DDU University, Gorakhpur, Indian Sociological Society, 2004, p. xii.

⁷ See Lalitha: "Relevance on National Policy on Social Sciences," -Abstracted in Manvendra Pratap Singh ed. 30 All India Sociological Conference, Gorakhpur, December 27-29, 2004, National Policy on Social Sciences, Souvenir &

till the time of writing, no policy on the social sciences has been announced by the Government of India. A brief overview of the development of policies on the social sciences is given in Appendix 1.

Suggested policy measures

We have seen that a social science policy evolved gradually in the colonial period. The British, in their own interest, initiated researches collecting data on the social, educational and other facets of Indian life. In the post-Independence era, the education policy went hand in hand with planning. Some think tanks and social science research centres were set up but no coherent policy on the social sciences was framed. I think that a National Policy on the Social Sciences is vitally necessary for their development. What should the components of such a policy be? I had previously suggested certain policy measures. (Banerjee, 2007) (Banerjee, 2013) With political change, I feel there is need to modify these policy measures.

1. Firstly, the basis of any policy on the social sciences should be strictly a secular policy.

The Concise Oxford Dictionary of Current English (9th ed., 1995) defines the word "secular" as "concerned with affairs of this world, not spiritual or sacred". In 2014, a new government has come to power in the centre. Since then, a wave of Hindutva is sweeping the country. The secular character of our country is in danger. What is more, an attempt is being made to saffronise science. The Vedas are claimed by the adherents of Hindutva as repositories of all scientific wisdom. Intellectuals have rightly criticized this stance.

Abstracts, Organized by Department of sociology, DDU University, Gorakhpur, Indian Sociological Society, 2004

(Mitra, 2015), (Guha, 2015), (Dutta, 2015). Any science, be it astronomy, chemistry or physics, has advanced because the stance of their practitioners was secular and rational. In the process, many of the early scientists, like Galileo, suffered untold humiliation at the hands of the religious authorities for speaking against orthodox Christian teachings. But, ultimately, science won the day.

We should keep in mind the words of the "Preamble" to The Constitution of India which declares India to be a "SOVEREIGN, SOCIALIST, SECULAR DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC". Let us resist by all means the attempt by fundamentalist forces to undermine the secular character of the Indian state. A National Policy on the Social Sciences in India should project a totally secular, rationalist outlook.

2. Secondly, the study of the social sciences should be integrated in the school curriculum at the primary level itself.

From primary school onwards, our students learn languages, History, Civics, Geography, Moral Science, Science, Mathematics and Computers. If they can learn so many subjects a course on Social Sciences would not be an added burden if it is properly designed. History, Geography and Civics may be replaced by a comprehensive course which will include elements of History, Political Science, Geography, Economics and Sociology. This course should be descriptive, rather than theoretical or conceptual.

3. Bilingualism should be followed in the teaching of the social sciences at the college and university level.

India is a land of many languages. Although The Constitution of India (Art.343) provided for English or Hindi as the official language of India.

But since India is a country of many languages, the Constitution included a list of recognized languages in the Eighth Schedule. Most students are comfortable in learning in their mother tongue. But, in many cases, we find that all standard textbooks are written in English. But I think that wherever it is possible, bilingualism should be adopted as the method of instruction in college and university level. In fact we practice bilingualism in Sociology Department of Burdwan University. I have contributed in my own way to bilingualism by publishing a bilingual book on Sociological Terminology

(Banerjee (Bandyopadhyay) Anirban, 2009) Knowing that most students are interested in learning sociology in their mother tongue, I have contributed to the popular understanding of sociological concepts and theories through a series of short essays on various sociological topics under the heading "Samajtattver Abhidhan" 8.

4. Social Scientists should be encouraged to do research through a liberal system of sabbatical leave.

Research is a tedious business. It requires time for study and reflection. Most social scientists doing research projects do not get leave from their institutes for doing research. On top of it

⁸ See Anirban Bandyopadhyaya: "Samajtattver Abhidhan", *Samajtattva* XIV(I), 2008; Anirban Bandyopadhyaya: "Samajtattver Abhidhan", *Samajtattva*, XIV (II) 2008, Anirban Bandyopadhyaya: "Samajtattver Abhidhan", *Samajtattva*, XV (I & II) 2009, Anirban Bandyopadhyaya: "Samajtattver Abhidhan", *Samajtattva* 16(1) 2010, Anirban Bandyopadhyaya: "Samajtattver Abhidhan", *Samajtattva* 16(2) 2010, Anirban Bandyopadhyaya: "Samajtattver Abhidhan", *Samajtattva* 18(1) 2012, Anirban Bandyopadhyaya: "Samajtattver Abhidhan", *Samajtattva* 18(2) 2012, Anirban Bandyopadhyaya: "Samajtattver Abhidhan", *Samajtattva* 19(1) 2012, Anirban Bandyopadhyaya: "Samajtattver Abhidhan", *Samajtattva* 19(2) 2012.

they are often burdened by administrative responsibilities, like Headship. I think that any scholar who is awarded a research project should be automatically given a sabbatical leave. Only then can the scientist do justice to his research.

5. Government should encourage interdisciplinary research and teaching .

Nowadays, no social science can remain isolated from other social sciences. Interdisciplinary research is essential if the research is to contribute in a major way to the advancement of knowledge and solve social problems. We have seen how the Joint Research Committee of the European Union has progressed through interdisciplinary research .I am happy to say that the University Grants Commission is encouraging interdisciplinary research. Any scholar who wishes to do a Research Project has to state the interdisciplinary relevance of the project .⁹ But it is not enough. Government should also encourage interdisciplinary courses for students in colleges and universities.

6. Study of regional issues should be emphasized.

India is a vast and variegated country. Every region of the country has its own unique peculiarities and its own set of problems which need to be studied in detail. Some of these problems may not be confined to the region .The All India Sociological Conferences devote a session to the problems of the region in which they are being held. While attending the 39th All India Sociological Conference in Mysore (2013) , I was listening to the speakers who

⁹ See Part B of *University Grants Commission :Research Project For Teachers, Major & Minor ,XI Plan Guidelines* ,University Grants Commission, Bahadur Shah Zafar Marg, New Delhi, p.18& 23.

dwelt on the problems of the Karnataka region. One panelist was speaking on health care issues in Karnataka. I was struck by the similarities of the problems faced by the people of Karnataka and West Bengal with regard to health care. While researchers study regional issues, do these researches percolate down to the students? Can we not teach our students the sociology of the region in which they live? Till now, our students are studying Indian society .But I find no paper in the syllabus where can teach students about Bengali society. I think a compulsory paper should be introduced in both the undergraduate and post-graduate syllabi which dwell on problems peculiar to the region.

7. A network of Social Science museums should be developed in each district.

Museums play a very important role in the dissemination and popularization of knowledge, whether historical or scientific. India has already a network of scientific museums in place thanks to efforts by the National Council of Scientific Museums. In my student days I read about the "Outlook Tower "which was promoted by Patrick Geddes . The "Outlook Tower "was actually a museum on regional society and regional cultures. At the Department of Sociology,Osmania University, which I once visited, I found a sociology museum .It was the work of a Faculty Member. I think a network of Social Science museums should be built in each district. A college or university may serve as a nodal centre for each museum .This museum will disseminate scientific knowledge about society.

8.Documentary films on social issues, should be made .

Films play a very important role in mass entertainment. Today ad films are being made to promote a variety of products. The

government is also using films for propaganda. I think the medium of the film may be used to highlight social issues before the people. Indian society has many social problems. 49.8 % of the people, for example, defecate in the open¹⁰. The problem is not merely a problem of lack of toilet facilities. It is a cultural problem as well. Similarly, the Saradha scam and the myriad chit funds like Rose Valley, MPS, ICORE, etc., in West Bengal and other parts of the country showed how easily people are cheated out of their hard earned money¹¹. This problem is not merely an economic issue, it is a cultural problem as well. Documentary films can be made on these and myriad other social issues, like dowry, female trafficking, child marriage, clean fuels, etc., and social scientists can be roped in as consultants. Screening of these documentaries should be made compulsory before the main show begins in cinema halls and multiplexes. These films can also be screened on Doordarshan and media policy should be modified to make private channels also screen such socially relevant films. Moreover, in schools and colleges throughout the country, a time slot should be created in the routine when these films will be screened for students.

9. The freedom of expression of social scientists should be protected.

The Article 19(1a) of the Constitution of India makes, "Freedom of Speech and

Expression", a Fundamental Right. But we find that this right is being violated everyday in one part of the country or another. Two recent

¹⁰ See "Cellphones outpace toilets in the country" *The Telegraph*, Calcutta, 14 March 2012.

¹¹ On Chitfund, see Merunil Dasgupta: "Chitfund: Kichu prasna, kichu sangsae", *Bartaman* 2 Baisakh, 1422.

incidents in Maharashtra and West Bengal may be mentioned here.

Mumbai, Maharashtra.

On Thursday, 16th April, 2015, BJP spokesperson, Shaina NC's father's office was allegedly vandalized by MNS workers in Mumbai. Shaina's father, Nana Chudasama, who runs an NGO "I love Mumbai", reportedly put up a banner criticizing the Maharashtra government's decision to make exhibition of Marathi films in multiplexes compulsory. The MNS workers vandalized his office, tearing down the banner, "PROMOTING MARATHI WELCOMED. DIKTAT NOT WELCOMED"¹². Nana Chudasama, however, was not intimidated by the goons. He replaced the torn banner.

Burdwan, West Bengal

On Friday, 17th February, 2015, some students, who had been distributing leaflets at the Golpabag campus of The University of Burdwan were allegedly assaulted by TMCP activists and arrested by the police¹³. The students were protesting against the failure of the authorities of The University of Burdwan to publish results of undergraduate examinations in time. When the results were published, they were found riddled with glaring mistakes. The students refused to be browbeaten and organized a protest demonstration at Curzon Gate in Burdwan, the next day, calling for the resignation of the Vice Chancellor¹⁴.

¹² Satyabrata Ray Goswami: "MNS WORKERS VANDALISE OFFICE: Banner ire at Shaina father" *The Telegraph*, Calcutta, 17 April, 2015, p.4.

¹³ See *Ananda Bazaar Patrika* "Bardhaman" 18 April, 2015.

¹⁴ See "Bardhamaner rastae mukhor 'hok pratibad'" -report in *Ananda Bazaar Patrika*, Kolkata, 19 April, 2015, p.18. See also Indranil Sarkar: "Burdwan University protest spills onto street", *The Telegraph*, Calcutta, 19 April, 2015, p.7.

Social scientists are, by profession, critics of society. The Government should ensure that their freedom of speech and expression is protected. They should not be dragged to court for any comment they make in their research papers or in public seminars. Protection from any form of harassment, either physical or legal, from either the lay public or the authorities in government should be built into a policy on the social sciences.

10. The corporate sector should play a role in education in the social sciences.

With the advent of globalization, the corporate sector is playing an important role in the education system. They are setting up colleges and universities. Mostly these colleges and universities are professional colleges where only professional courses are taught. Professional courses are those disciplines which are exclusively designed to cater to specific vocations and professions of modern society. (Banerjee, 2003, p. 86). These courses, like engineering and management are money spinners. Hence, corporates take an active interest in these courses. A rare exception is the Tata Institute of Social Sciences, which has become a leading private institute on social sciences even before the advent of globalization.

I think that in the age of globalization, the corporations should be made to invest in education in the social sciences. Nowadays there has emerged the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is the process by which companies manage their business to produce an overall positive effect on society. (Ray, 2011, p. 157) As part of their overall CSR strategy,

corporate bodies should be made to invest in education in the social sciences. They can do it in many ways, by sponsoring Chairs in universities, by offering scholarships to needy but meritorious students prosecuting a course in the social sciences or by opening colleges and universities where social sciences are given priority.

11. The employment potential of social sciences of social sciences should be improved

Education in modern society is tied to career development. One reason why professional courses get top priority among meritorious youth is that they automatically lead to a career upon completion of the course. The same observation cannot be made about the social sciences. Most students know very little about the career prospects of social sciences. Very rarely pullouts of well known dailies like The Telegraph (Careergraph) project social sciences like Sociology as viable career options. As a teacher of Sociology I have been seriously concerned about job prospects of the social sciences. I regularly counsel students on their career prospects and have also written a career guide on Sociology. (Banerjee (Bandyopadhyay), 2003) I think that any policy on the social sciences should give priority to improving the employment potential of the social sciences.

12. Sociologists should engage in policy research

Finally, I think that sociologists should engage in policy research. Sociologists should not merely do research for the sake of research. They should try to make active interventions in the improvement of social life. This will increase the

relevance of their discipline. I agree with Yogendra Singh on this point. He observed that :

The most widely acknowledged level of social science relevance relates to the contributions researchers make in formulation and implementation of policies of social welfare and development . (Singh, 2005, p. 196)

During the sixties, according to Singh, most researches in the social sciences were conducted in policy relevant areas in the form of urban surveys, demographic studies, village studies and evaluation of community development schemes and panchayat raj systems, etc. (Singh, 2005, p. 197). But how far have these studies actually influenced government policy?

In this age of globalization, when every subject of study is being assessed in terms of their relevance to society, to job prospects etc., there is need for social scientists to more and more engage in policy research. Only then can we justify our existence. A national policy on social sciences should also include a strategy by which works of social scientists can be fruitfully utilized for human development.

Concluding remarks

To conclude , a National Policy on the Social Sciences is vitally necessary for the proper development of the social sciences. In an earlier study , we have seen that interest in the social sciences is on decline in the West where they are cutting budgets .But China is investing heavily in the social sciences , which is in her national interest . (Banerjee, 2013, p. 21) In a developing country like India, it is in her

national interest to invest in the social sciences. In a country steeped in illiteracy, superstition and other evils ,an education in the social sciences is a must .If the country is to prosper, the fruits of the research of social scientists have to be properly utilized.

APPENDIX

DEVELOPMENT OF A NATIONAL POLICY ON THE SOCIAL SCIENCES IN INDIA

DEVELOPMENTS IN THE SOCIAL SCIENCES	POLICY IMPLICATIONS
A.THE BRITISH COLONIAL REGIME	A.THE BRITISH COLONIAL REGIME
A1. 1769.Henry Verelst, Governor of Bengal, stressed the necessity of collecting data on leading families of Bengal.	A1. This statement marks the beginning of the British Government's policy on the social sciences
A2.1787.Asiatic Society founded by Sir William Jones.	A2.The Asiatic Society won the support of the British Government.Indology was founded
A3.1807.Francis Buchanan undertakes the first ethnographic survey of Bengal	A3.Governor General in council commissioned the survey .Thus began the policy of collecting ethnographic data under government sponsorship.
A4.1822.Thomas Munro orders an enquiry into the state of indigenous education, which covers all districts except Kanara.	A4.-A.7.These colonial surveys on indigenous education collected data for the purpose of determining the future education policy in India. In the process, they collected a wealth of sociological data.
A5.1823.Monstuart Elphinstone 's	

enquiry into indigenous education in Bombay	
A6.Judicial department collects statistics on education	
A7.1835-1838.Adams makes a special enquiry into education in Bengal	
A8.1871.The first Census was undertaken in India by the British Indian Government. It would later become a decennial exercise.	A8.The Census systematized collection of sociological and anthropological data.
A9.1906.National Council of Education established by activists spearheading the Swadeshi Movement in Bengal .	A9.An indigenous education policy is founded in Bengal
A10.1914.The Government of India gives a grant to The University of Bombay to start a Department of Sociology	A10.Sociology wins official recognition from the British Government as a field of study .
A11.1917.The first Department of Sociology in India is inaugurated in Mysore University then under the Vice chancellorship of Brojendranath Seal .Mysore was then a native state	A11.Sociology becomes a field of study in an Indian native state .Indians take the lead to study sociology .

A.12.1919. The first Department of Sociology in British India is inaugurated in The University of Bombay. The noted urban sociologist, Prof.Patrick Geddes , was the first Head of the Department of the Department of Sociology and Civics.	A.12.Sociology which won official recognition from the British Government as a field of study inaugurated at The University of Bombay .Bombay University was to play a key role in the development of sociology in the coming decades.
A13.1921.Lucknow University established a combined Department of Sociology and Social Anthropology	A13.The study of Sociology continues to spread to different universities of British India under British patronage.Lucknow University is an example.
A14.1928.Sociology was first introduced at the undergraduate level at The University of Mysore.	A14.A major step is taken towards the popularization of Sociology by incorporating it at the undergraduate level. It paved the way for development of Sociology as a social science through training of young sociologists.
A15.The Anthropological Survey of India becomes a full fledged research organization under B.S.Guha , who served as its first Director.	A15.The Government realized the need for anthropological research .Even today this organization plays a key role in collecting data about tribals and shaping tribal policy.
B.INDEPENDENT INDIA	B.INDEPENDENT INDIA
B1.1947-48.University Education	B1.TheRadhakrishnanCommission recommended opening new fields of

Commission(Radhakrishnan Commission)-the first Education Commission in Independent India	study in higher education, including sociology.
B2.11 December,1951.Indian Sociological Society founded in Bombay under the Societies Registration Act, with G.S.Ghurye as the first President.	B2.The establishment of Indian Sociological Society institutionalized Indian Sociology .The Society is the only all India professional body of Indian sociologists.
B3.National Scientific Policy Resolution, Government of India	B3.Acting according to this resolution, the Government of India set up many research organizations. The Planning Commission set up a Research Programmes Committee for financing social science research .The bulk of the research funds, however, went to Economics.
B4.Planning Commission recommends setting up of the Indian Council of Social Science Research.	B4.Indian Council of Social Science Research (ICSSR) was founded in 1969.
B5.1966 .Education Commission (Kothari Commission)	B5. Kothari Commission recommended Socially Useful and Productive Work (SUPW) in school. No policy statement made on social sciences
B6. 1968.National Policy on Education	B6. National Policy on Education(1968) made no policy recommendations on the social sciences.
B7.1986. National	B7.National Policy on

Policy on Education	Education(1986) proposed to give adequate support to teaching and research in the social sciences. At the Bachelor's degree level, a provision was made to incorporate Sociology with Economics,Commerce,social work, Labour Welfare and Trade Unions. The University Grants Commission prepared a Model Syllabus on sociology and other disciplines.
B8.2004.XXXAll India Sociological Conference held at Gorakpur, Uttar Pradesh(December 27-29,2004).	B8.2004.At the XXX All India Sociological Conference renowned sociologists extensively discussed National Policy on the Social Sciences.Two symposia were arranged. Symposium 1.National Policy on the Social Sciences:Institutional dimensions of Social Science Policy. Symposium 2. .National Policy on the Social Science:Policy considerations in promotion of Excellence in Teaching and Research
B9.2005.The Government of India appoints renowned sociologist, André Beteille , as Chairman of Indian Council of Social	B9.2005.These steps show that the government was giving recognition to sociologists.

<p>Science Research. Other leading sociologists , like J.J.Kattakayam, former Secretary of Indian Sociological Society , who later became its President were appointed as members of ICSSR. André Beteille was later appointed as one of the members of National Knowledge Commission under the Chairmanship of Sam Pitroda</p>	
<p>B10.2005.The XXXI All India Sociological conference was held in Jammu in October 2005.</p>	<p>B10.2005.The conference devoted two sessions to teaching and research in Sociology and one session to problems of the Jammu & Kashmir region. No policy implications for the social sciences.</p>

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